

7th International Symposium on Surface Imaging/Spectroscopy at the Solid/Liquid Interface

JUNE 5th – 7th, 2024, Kraków, Poland

organized by

**Jerzy Haber Institute of Catalysis and Surface Chemistry
Polish Academy of Sciences
and
Faculty of Chemistry of the Jagiellonian University**

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**Jerzy Haber Institute of Catalysis and Surface Chemistry
Polish Academy of Sciences
2024, Kraków, Poland**

ISBN 978-83-60514-38-2

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Polish Academy of Sciences

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Structure evolution, adhesion and mechanical properties of nanostructural layered double hydroxide coatings developed on Zn alloy

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Zinc alloys next to magnesium alloys are starting to play an increasingly promising role in biomedical–related applications. However, their main drawbacks include poor corrosion and wear resistance, which readily result in the reduction of functional properties. Implementation of coatings with layered double hydroxides (LDHs) structure allows the creation of smart biodegradable materials with enhanced corrosion resistance, biocompatibility, and controllable degradation. This project will focus on a deeper correlation between the structural aspects of LDHs and their hardness, roughness, and adhesion performance in bio–relevant applications. In this study, we focus on the development of LDH structure, directly grown on a Zn surface using the substrate alloy as an internal source of Zn cations to form naturally adherent coatings. The incorporation of corrosion inhibitors and further deposition of chitosan film will be the next step to provide a natural biopolymer with good biocompatibility, and antibacterial activity.

A series of ZnAl–NO₃ LDH coatings with the formula of $[M^{2+}_{1-x}M^{3+}_x(OH)_2][An^-]_{x/n} \cdot mH_2O$ (where M^{2+} and M^{3+} are respectively two– and three–positive cations) were obtained in situ on the surface of Zn alloys under the control of pH.

The effects of the preparation methods, the time of growth, on the thickness and structure of LDH coatings were comparatively investigated with the use of SEM/BSE/EDS, X–ray diffraction methods as well as advanced XPS and FTIR spectroscopies towards the formation of a dense LDH layer on the Zn alloy surface. EDS analysis showed the presence of Zn and Al in the micro–areas of the formed LDH layer. The amount of Al in micro–areas increases with progressive synthesis time, which confirms the crystallization of the hydroxide–like layer on the Zn alloy surface. XRD and FTIR analysis revealed the changes in the LDH layer as a function of exposure time to the solution containing Al³⁺ ions.

Fig.1. SEM images, EDS, and FTIR analysis, as well as scratch tests of ZnAl–NO₃ LDHs coatings developed on Zn alloy after aging.

The micro– and nano–mechanical properties of the synthesized nanostructural LDH deposited on Zn metal alloy substrates were evaluated. A correlation between the coating surface roughness and the roughness of the Zn alloy substrate was found in the study of the geometric structure of the coating surfaces. The hardness and elastic modulus were assessed using the nano–indentation technique. The prolongation of the synthesis process increased the thickness of the ZnAl–LDH structure. The coating obtained after 20 h of growth showed higher hardness ($H_{IT}=600$ MPa) than the ZnAl–NO₃ LDHs/Zn alloy–3h coating ($H_{IT}=505$ MPa). Micro–scratch tests were done to determine the coating’s adhesion to the substrate. The results of the scratch investigation indicated the sufficient adhesion of the coatings to the substrates.

Acknowledgment

We gratefully acknowledge the support of the National Science Centre of Poland, grant 2021/40/C/ST5/00266. This work was partially supported by AGH University of Science and Technology, research program No. 16.16.130.942.